

Supplementary Material for

Phylogenomics of scorpions reveal contemporaneous diversification of scorpion mammalian predators and mammal-active sodium channel toxins

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SUPPLEMENTARY TEXT

Taxon sampling

Sequences from 100 species of Scorpiones were used for this study, of which 56 were sequenced previously by our team and 43 were newly sequenced for this study. In addition, transcriptomes of 20 outgroup taxa representing seven chelicerate orders were included. A full list of sequences, with taxonomic information, sources of previously published sequenced, and GenBank accession numbers, is provided in Supplementary Tables S1-3.

RNA extraction and sequencing

All specimens were either collected in the field with the aid of UV illumination, or from captive bred colonies (Table S2). From all specimens, the brain, legs and telson were dissected for sequencing, as in our previous publications (Santibáñez-López et al. 2019). For surveying transcriptional activity of venom gland tissue, scorpion venom glands were drained using a Parafilm membrane stretched across a 35-mm Petri dish target. All tissues were dissected into RNAlater solution (Ambion, Foster City, CA, USA). Total RNA extraction with TriZOL Trireagent (Ambion Life Technologies, Waltham, MA, USA), mRNA purification, and cDNA library construction using Illumina Tru-Seq kits were performed using manufacturers' protocols, as detailed in our recent works (Sharma et al. 2014; 2015; Santibáñez-López et al. 2018a; 2018b). Library preparation and stranded mRNA sequencing was performed at the Biotechnology Center at the University of Wisconsin-Madison or using an Apollo

324 automated system using the PrepX mRNA kit (IntegenX, Pleasanton, CA, USA) at Harvard University's Bauer Core Facility, with samples marked with unique indices to enable multiplexing. Samples were run using the Illumina HiSeq 2500 platform with paired-end reads of 100 or 150 bp at the FAS Center for Systems Biology at Harvard University, and using an Illumina HiSeq 2500 High Throughput platform with paired-end reads of 125-150 bp at the Biotechnology Center at the University of Wisconsin-Madison.

De novo transcriptome assemblies and orthology inference

Newly generated transcriptomes were assembled using Trinity v.2.5 (Trinity --seqType fq --SS_lib_type RF --left Scorpion_R1.fastq.gz --right Scorpion_R2.fastq.gz --CPU 6 --max_memory 60G --trimmomatic --full_cleanup - -output ./Scorpion_LIBRARY_trinity; Grabherr et al. 2011), removing the adaptors with Trimmomatic v.0.36 (Bolger et al. 2014) and assessing the quality of cleaned raw reads with FastQC v.0.11.5 (Andrews 2010). Protein coding regions within the assembled transcripts were identified using TransDecoder v. 5.3.0 (TransDecoder.LongOrfs -t Scorpion_LIBRARY_trinity.fasta -m 75; TransDecoder.Predict -t Scorpion_LIBRARY_trinity.fasta; Haas et al. 2013). *De novo* phylogenetic orthology resulted prohibitive for a dataset of this size. To overcome this limitation, we leveraged a dataset of 3564 orthologous loci established for 53 chelicerates and outgroups, as described by Ballesteros and Sharma (2019). This dataset was previously established using a phylogenetically-informed criterion for orthology inference and was extensively

investigated for sources of systematic bias and signal (Ballesteros and Sharma 2019). The untrimmed alignment of each pre-computed orthogroup was used to produce a hidden Markov profile using *hmmrbuid* (`hmmrbuid dataset_loci.fasta loci`) from *hmmr* package v.3.2.1 (Finn et al. 2011). Each proteome/transcriptome of the species of interest was then searched (`hmmrsearch loci scorpion_transcriptomes.fasta > new_scorpion_loci.out`) for matches against the collection of profiles with an expectation threshold of $e < 10^{-20}$; for cases with more than one hits per locus, the sequence with the best score was selected, and the corresponding sequence appended to the locus FASTA file aggregating the putative orthologous found in each species.

These putative orthogroups was further refined by comparing each of its sequences against the proteome of the fruit fly *Drosophila melanogaster* (NCBI UP000000803), identifying the most common best hit fruit fly gene and removing from the orthogroup all sequences pointing to a different best-hit with *D. melanogaster*. Note that this filter does not require that *D. melanogaster* is included in an orthogroup.

Phylogenetic methods

From this collection of orthologs, gene trees were estimated using IQTREE v.1.6. (Nguyen et al. 2014) implementing the best-fitting amino acid substitution model inferred by ModelFinderPlus (Kalyaanamoorthy et al. 2017) and 1000 ultrafast bootstrapping replicates (Hoang et al. 2018) (`iqtree -s ScorpOrthogroup -m MFP -bb 1000`). Subsequently, these orthologs were subject

to a relaxed occupancy filtering and finally, each gene tree was visually examined for paralogy, in tandem with validation of homology of ambiguous sequences using SMART-BLAST; when detected, individual paralogs were removed. As an example, the sequence of *M. martensii* (shown in red in Figure A1, below) could be either a paralog or a fragmentary sequence (or both). Upon examination, the sequence turned out to be significantly shorter than the rest of the sequences in the alignment, significantly misaligned, and SMART-BLAST recovered a different annotation for this sequence than for the remaining scorpion sequences. Therefore, it was removed from the alignment.

Because most sequences of *M. martensii* featured this issue (long patristic distances in gene trees, together with fragmentary transcripts and anomalous placement with outgroups), this species was removed from our main analyses and its placement was assessed separately, after retaining a very small number of correctly aligned sequences from this dataset (see below).

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Fig. A1. Exemplar gene tree showing approach to detection of paralogs. Blue: scorpions. Red: Ambiguous sequence of *Mesobuthus martensii* (a highly incomplete Roche 454 pyrosequenced genome).

Three matrices were assembled with a minimal taxon occupancy threshold. For Matrix 1, we retained loci representing at least 115 species per ortholog; for Matrix 2, at least 109 species per ortholog; and for Matrix 3, at least 103 species per ortholog. Matrix 1 consisted of 192 loci and 53,333 sites (>95% complete), Matrix 2 consisted of 424 loci and 114,188 sites (>90% complete), and Matrix 3 consisted of 660 loci and 185,631 sites (>85% complete).

Phylogenetic inference of these concatenated matrices was computed with IQ-TREE v.2.0.6 (Minh et al. 2020a) implementing the best-fitting amino acid substitution per partition as selected in our gene tree estimation (-spp). Nodal support was estimated using ultrafast bootstrapping (Hoang et al. 2018), and concordance factors (Minh et al. 2020b). Using the recollection of gene trees, we calculated the gene concordance factor (gCF) and the site concordance factor (sCF) using 100 quartets (e.g. `iqtree2 -t AL115.concat.treefile.tree --gcf AL115.loci.treefile.trees -s ScorpAL115.phy --scf 100 --prefix concord_AL115 -T 4`). Species tree estimation of the constituent orthologs of the three matrices were generated using the collection of ML gene trees and computed with ASTRAL v.3 (e.g. `java -jar astral.5.5.7.jar -i all_ready_AL115.tre -o Astral_AL115.tre`; Mirarab and Warnow 2015). Lastly, while Bayesian inference analysis was explored for Matrix 3 (>95 complete) using PhyloBayes-mpi v.1.7 (Lartillot et al. 2013) under a CAT + GTR + Γ_4 model (`mpirun -np 4 pb_mpi -d AL103.phy -cat -gtr -dgam 4 -dc -t start.tre chtc_scorpio_run`) failed to converge after over eight months of computation time on four independent chains; results from the PhyloBayes-mpi run are not shown.

To explore information content and identify potential biases in our phylogenomic matrices, we analyzed our three main datasets using Phykit v.1.5.0 (Steenwyk et al. 2021). Metrics compared across loci in the three matrices consisted of the number of sites per locus, the number of sites without gaps (for i in *.fa; do phykit aln_len_no_gaps \$i > Alignment_length/\${i%%.*}_aln_len.txt; done), the number of parsimony-informative sites per locus (for i in *.fa; do phykit pis \$i > ps-sites/\${i%%.*}_ps.txt; done), bipartition support per locus (for i in *.tre; do phykit bss \$i > Bipartition/\${i%%.*}_bp.txt; done), and long branch score per locus (for i in *.tre; do phykit lb_score \$i -verbose > LB_scores/\${i%%.*}_lb_ext.txt; done) (Fig. S1). To compare saturation curves (Figs. S2, S3), we constructed plots of uncorrected versus model-correct patristic distances of individual genes. For these plots, we calculated the slope and the correlation of the regression (R^2) using TreSpEx v.1.1 (perl TreSpEx.v1.pl -fun g -ipt AL115trees.txt -ipa AL115alignments.txt -path ./; Struck, 2014), as well as a script previously published by our team (Ballesteros et al. 2019).

Phylogenetic analyses for data-poor terminals

To further explore the validity of higher level buthid systematics, previously defined on the basis of trichobothrial position on the surface of the pedipalps (*sensu* Fet et al. 2005), we searched GenBank for molecular data available for phylogenetically significant scorpion genera and species not sequenced in this study (Supplementary Table S4). We add nine RNA-Seq datasets and one

Sanger-sequenced EST dataset. The orthology inference of the 10 species was conducted as for the main analyses, using the collection of orthologs of our Matrix 2. This augmented matrix is henceforth referred to as “M2plus”.

In addition, we thereafter added Sanger-sequenced data for 10 species (representing buthid genera for which RNA-seq datasets are not available). Sanger-sequenced loci included in our analyses were cytochrome *c* oxidase subunit I (COI), 16S ribosomal RNA, and 18S rRNA. Sequences of these loci were also included for the rest of our study taxa, where available. The resulting matrix (“M2.plus.sanger”) was analyzed using maximum likelihood.

Preliminary phylogenetic analyses of the M2plus and M2.plus.sanger matrices were performed using IQ-TREE, implementing the best-fitting nucleotide substitution model inferred with ModelFinderPlus, and ultrafast bootstrapping (iqtree -spp AlignmentM2p.sanger.nex -bb 1000).

Divergence time estimation

It is well known that performing divergence time estimation with large, modern datasets is notoriously computationally intensive. Thus, Matrix 1 was selected to estimate dates of divergence based on its high taxon occupancy and lower values of missing data. Divergence time estimation was performed using mcmctree v.4.8 (mcmctree mcmctree_AL103.ctl) and codeml v.4.8 (codeml tmp0001.ctl) from the PAML software package v.4.8 (Yang 2007) using the approximate likelihood method (dos Reis and Yang 2011, 2019). The input tree was the best ML topology from the analysis of Matrix 2 (selected for its resolution

of buthid internal relationships) and was time-calibrated using 15 calibration points. These points were selected based on several references and are listed in the Supplementary Table S5. Nine outgroup calibration points were implemented as minimum bounds with uniform priors; six scorpion calibration points were implemented as with minimum and maximum bounds; and the root age was implemented as a hard maximum bound. A conservative age constraint on the basal diversification of Arachnida was applied (see *Fossil calibrations*, below).

As suggested by other studies (i.e. Kawahara et al. 2019), the Dirichlet-Gamma density (dos Reis et al. 2014) was used to set the prior on the molecular rate with the default parameters ($\alpha_{\mu} = 2$, $\beta_{\mu} = 6$, $\alpha = 1$). Similarly, the default parameters for the birth-death process were kept ($\lambda = 1$, $\rho = 0.1$). Independent-rates and the correlated rates models were selected to perform the divergence time estimation. Hessian matrices were calculated with codeml using empirical base frequencies and the LG substitution model with 5 rate categories. A burn-in of 25,000, sample frequency of 100, and a sample size of 25,000 (resulting in a 2.5 million generations) for each of the two clock models was implemented. Each analysis was repeated four times, with the convergence subsequently evaluated in Tracer v. 1.7.1 (Rambaut et al. 2018) and by plotting the node ages against each other in R (data available upon request). Lastly, the four chains were merged to achieve large effective sample sizes (ESS > 200) and produce the summary tree. The resulting topology was plotted using the function *MCMC.tree.plot* from the R package MCMCtreeR v.1.1 (Puttick 2019).

Fossil calibrations

The oldest putative fossil scorpion, *Parioscorpio venator*, was recently discovered and dates to the Silurian (436.5-437.5 Mya; Wendruff et al. 2020), slightly pushing back the age of the oldest stem-group Scorpiones as inferred from fossils like *Dolichophonus loudenensis* and *Eramoscorpium brucensis*. However, recently Anderson et al. (2021) showed evidence suggesting *P. venator* is not a scorpion. Therefore, for our analysis, we used the date of *E. brucensis* to set the minimum age for the stem-group. The oldest crown group scorpion (Orthosterni) is Carboniferous in age (*Protoischnurus axelrodorum*) (reviewed by Wolfe et al. 2016). We constrained the stem age of scorpions (divergence from outgroup taxa) using a soft minimum of 435.15 Mya and a soft maximum of 514 Mya, with the upper bound following an established calibration strategy for arthropods (Wolfe et al. 2016). We constrained crown Orthosterni with a soft maximum age of 313.7 Mya and a soft minimum age of 112.6 Mya, based on the age of *Compsoscorpium buthiformis*, a fossil Scorpionoidea (Poiton et al. 2012). Given the clear affinity of *Protoischnurus axelrodorum* as a lineage within Lurida (Menton 2007), Lurida was also constrained using soft bounds of 112.6 to 313.7 Mya. Chaerilidae was constrained using a soft minimum age of 98.17 Mya, based on the age of *Electrochaerilus buckleyi* (Santiago-Blay et al. 2004a) and a soft maximum age of 313.7 Mya. We constrained Buthoidea using a soft minimum of 49.26 Mya, based on the age of *Uintascorpium halandrasi* (Perry 1995, Santiago-Blay et al. 2004b) and a soft maximum age of 313.7 Mya, given the sister group relationship of Buthida and Lurida. Finally, the superfamily

Scorpioidea was constrained with a soft minimum of 112.6 Mya, based on the age of *Compsoscorpius buthiformis*, and a soft maximum of 313.7 Mya. Further discussion of these fossils is provided in a recent review (Howard et al. 2019). Ten additional outgroup calibrations were deployed for the remaining chelicerate orders, using only soft minimum calibrations. We constrained the crown group of Opiliones using the soft minimum age of 411 Mya, based on the harvestman fossil *Eophalangium sheari* (Garwood et al. 2014), the divergence of Eupnoi harvestmen with a soft minimum age of 305 Mya, based on the age of *Macroglyon cronus* (Garwood et al. 2011); and the divergence of Dyspnoi harvestmen with a soft minimum age of 305 Mya, based on the age of *Ameticoscolos* (Garwood et al. 2011). The age of Araneae was calibrated with a soft minimum age of 386 Mya, based on the fossil *Attercopus fimbriunguis* (Selden et al. 2008, Huang et al. 2018). The stem-group age of Mesothelae was calibrated with a soft minimum age of 305 Mya, based on the unambiguous mesothele fossil *Palaeothele montceauensis* (Selden 1996). The stem-group age of Amblypygi was bounded with a soft minimum age of 312 Mya based on the fossils *Graeophonus anglicus* and *G. carbonarius* (Dunlop et al. 2007). The crown group of Pseudoscorpiones was calibrated with a soft minimum age of 392 Mya, based on the age of *Dracochela deprehendor* (Schawaller et al. 1991). Finally, the stem-group age of Xiphosura was constrained with a soft minimum age of 445 Mya, corresponding to the age of *Lunataspis aurora* (Rudkin et al. 2008).

Maximum bounds were omitted for outgroup orders, because these are nuisance parameters and the fossil record of many of these groups is too

poor to facilitate the selection of reasonable maximum bounds. As an intuitive example, the oldest known arachnid fossils are those of scorpions from the Silurian (e.g., *Eramoscorpius brucensis*, ca. 435 Mya). It has been recently shown that scorpions are likely nested deeply within Arachnopulmonata, as the sister group of pseudoscorpions (Ontano et al. 2021). It then stands to reason that (at least stem-group) Pseudoscorpiones and Tetrapulmonata had diversified by the Silurian as well. The absence of groups like Pedipalpi for another ca. 120 million years after the appearance of *E. brucensis* implies that the fossil record of terrestrial chelicerates is too sparse for reasonable application of maximum age bounds. Given that the diversity of these outgroup orders is also poorly sampled, we restricted the use of maximum age bounds only to scorpions, which have a comparatively richer Paleozoic record.

Gene tree analyses and molecular evolution of venom scorpion peptides

Cysteine-stabilized α -helix and β -sheet fold ($CS_{\alpha\beta}$), disulfide-directed beta-hairpin (DDH) and inhibitor cystine knot (ICK) homologs from scorpion venom were retrieved from our concatenated transcriptome libraries using a query files with known $CS_{\alpha\beta}$ - ICK - DDH sequences from the venom of scorpions (i.e. sodium channel toxins, potassium channel toxins, chloride channel toxins, scorpines, Kunitz-type inhibitors, and calcins). Matching sequences with low e-values ($e < 1 \times 10^{-15}$) were selected. Subsequently, these selected sequences were concatenated with 789 sequences from scorpion venom peptides retrieved from UniProt and InterPro (Supplementary Table S6).

Preliminary ML phylogenetic analyses were conducted using the entire dataset and IQ-TREE (iqtree -s ICK_CSab_DDH_dataset.fasta -m MFP -bb 1000), with the resulting trees analyzed in search of orthologs. We removed sequences retrieved from our transcriptomes that were recovered outside clades with at least one known venom sequence. Our final dataset consisted of 1,353 CS $\alpha\beta$ - ICK scorpion sequences and 41 DDH scorpion toxin sequences as outgroup. Clades were delimited manually based on the presence of well-known scorpion toxins (Supplementary Table S6). Thus, the sodium channel toxins (NaTx) dataset consisted of 661 sequences, the potassium channel toxins (KTx) dataset of 550, the chloride channel toxins (CITx) dataset of 56, and the calcin dataset of 74 sequences. Multiple sequence alignments for sequences from each clade were constructed using MAFFT v.7.4 with default parameters (Kato and Standley 2013) and gene trees were generated using IQ-TREE implementing ModelFinderPlus and ultrafast bootstrapping (e.g. iqtree -s NaTx_dataset.fasta -m MFP -bb 1000). The topology of NaTx (Figure 3B) was plotted and annotated with the Iroki webapp (<https://www.iroki.net/>; Moore et al. 2020). Our annotations included the names of the parvorders (e.g., Lurida), family (e.g., Pseudochactidae) or buthid species groups. In addition, we included the names of the NaTx clades recovered from our ML analyses. Lastly, we include the annotations for sequences with known functions and affinities.

The signal peptides, propeptides and mature peptides were predicted for the sequences in each clade using SpiderP from Arachnoserver (Herzig et al 2010). To determine if convergent sites predates the origin of different clades of

mammal-active toxins within NaTx, motifs from the mature peptide (the active component of the toxin) were generated using the Multiple Em for Motif Elicitation server (MEME v.5.1.1 at <http://meme-suite.org/tools/meme>; Bailey et al. 2015). Gene trees and multiple sequence alignment were plotted using the extended R package ggmsa v.1.0.2 from ggplot2 v.3.3.5 (Wickham, 2016) with the function *geom_facet*. Consensus sequences were obtained for each subclade recovered in our gene tree analyses using JalView v.2.11 (Waterhouse et al. 2009). These consensus sequences were then aligned to one representative sequence with known affinity from each clade in JalView (Supplementary Figure S19).

Additionally, the mature peptides of the amino acid sequences from the two main clades recovered in the ML analysis of the NaTx (Aah2-like and Cn2-like) were used for CLANS v.29.05.2012 cluster analysis (java -jar clans.jar clans.conf; Frickey and Lupas 2004) with the default parameters as stated in the configuration file.

The distribution of the different scorpion toxins in their corresponding clades (as recovered by our gene tree analyses), and the species hierarchical taxonomic category were mapped as an alluvial plot with the R package ggplot2 and the function *geom_alluvium*. In addition, the diversity of selected transcripts (e.g. number of NaTx, calcins, or KTx) was mapped as a function of a heatmap and the scorpion phylogeny with the extended R package ggtree v.2.5.1 (function *gheatmap*; Yu, 2020) from ggplot2.

Phylostratigraphic bracketing approach to infer the origins and ages of mammal-active toxins

To infer the origins of mammal-active toxins in scorpion venom, we used phylostratigraphic bracketing, an approach that uses minimum-spanning clades as a minimum age estimate for age of origin. Based on our annotated NaTx with Iroki, we traced the origin of toxins present in the venom of closely related scorpions. As a hypothetical example, if a toxin with known mammalian ion channel affinity belongs to a *Tityus* species (i.e., was sequenced from a *Tityus* and was recovered in a cluster containing other venom sequences of *Tityus* species), we inferred the origin of that toxin to be at least present by the stem-age of that node (the stem-age of *Tityus*). Using this approach, we conservatively identified eight different origins of mammal sodium channel affinity, which corresponded to four nodes in the species tree: *Centruroides*, *Tityus*, *Parabuthus* and the *Buthus* group. We corroborated independent origins of mammal-active toxins using the output of CLANS clustering, which recovered several well-separated clusters of NaTx sequences. When annotated for toxin affinity, mammal-active toxins formed eight independent clusters, reinforcing the inference of independent origins of mammal ion channel affinity.

To infer the age of the mammal-active toxins in scorpion venom, we used the stem age of the most inclusive buthid clades containing those species with known mammal-active toxins as a proxy for the minimum estimate of gene age. The posterior distribution of the stem ages of *Centruroides*, *Tityus*, *Parabuthus*

and the *Buthus* group were retrieved from our mcmcree results, and plotted using MCMCtreeR.

To compare these results to the ages of scorpion predators, we obtained the 95% Highest Posterior Density (95% HPD) interval for the node ages of Didelphimorphia, Eulipotyphia, Chiroptera, Carnivora and Rodentia from the phylogenetic works of Meredith et al. (2011) and Upham et al. (2019). These HPD intervals were plotted using MCMCtreeR to evaluate overlap and temporal sequence of toxin and predator origins.

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Supplementary Figure S1. Violin plots summarizing information content in the three matrices. The long branch score can be used as a measure of heterogeneity by identifying taxa that can contribute to long branch issues. Similarly, the bipartition support statistics aims to provide certainty among bipartitions within each gene partition.

Supplementary Figure S2. Saturation per-locus measured as a function of the slope for genes in Matrices 1-3.

Supplementary Figure S3. Estimations of slope and the correlation coefficient for Matrices 1 (green), 2 (purple), and 3 (brown), implementing a y-intercept as shown in Ballesteros et al. (2019).

Supplementary Figure S4. Maximum likelihood tree topology recovered from the analysis of 192 loci (Matrix 1). Numbers above nodes indicate bootstrap support values, below nodes indicate gene concordance factor (gCF) and the site concordance factor (sCF). Bottom panel shows an overview of the three matrices.

Supplementary Figure S5. Maximum likelihood tree topology recovered from the analysis of 424 loci (Matrix 2). Numbers above nodes indicate bootstrap support values. Bottom panel shows an overview of the three matrices.

Supplementary Figure S6. Maximum likelihood tree topology recovered from the analysis of 660 loci (Matrix 3). Numbers above nodes indicate bootstrap support values. Bottom panel shows an overview of the three matrices.

Supplementary Figure S7. Maximum likelihood tree topology of Buthida recovered from the analysis of a combined dataset consisting of 424 genes (Matrix 2) and 2,692 nucleotides corresponding to three genes (18S rRNA, 16S rRNA, and COI). Color coding indicates species groups delimited by Fet et al. (2005).

Supplementary Figure S8. ASTRAL trees recovered from gene trees constituting Matrix 1 (left), Matrix 2 (center), and Matrix 3 (right). Numbers indicate branch support from local posterior probabilities.

Supplementary Figure S9. Summary of scorpion time tree showing the diversity of venom components in the different families and genera. Data were obtained from transcriptomic resources and databases (UniProt and InterPro).

Supplementary Figure S10. Maximum likelihood evolutionary tree for CS $\alpha\beta$ -ICK gene families (top left) and KTx gene families (top right). ML evolutionary trees for CS $\alpha\beta$ (bottom left) and ICK-DDH (bottom right) inferred independently from each other.

Supplementary Figure S11. Maximum likelihood gene tree recovered from the analysis of 74 ryanodine receptor ligand peptides (calcins) and three disulphide-directed beta-hairpin (DDH) genes as outgroups. Calcins are ubiquitous in iurid scorpion venom as shown on the inset scorpion phylogeny.

Supplementary Figure S12. Maximum likelihood gene tree recovered from the analysis of 56 chloride channel toxin (CITx) peptides and seven outgroups. CITx are unique to buthid scorpions as shown on the inset scorpion phylogeny.

Supplementary Figure S13. Maximum likelihood gene tree recovered from the analysis of 723 Sodium channel toxin (NaTx) peptides recovered from our transcriptomic analyses and databases (UniProt and InterPro), plus two outgroups (inset). Multiple sequence alignment color-coded for the 294 peptides from the Aah2-like clade (highlighted in black on inset phylogeny). Mature peptide repetitive motifs found using Multiple Em for Motif Elicitation (MEME) locations as shown by colored bars.

Supplementary Figure S14. Left: Pruned gene tree of the Aah2-like clade consisting of species from the *Buthus* group. Two sequences from *Babycurus gigas* might be cross contamination from the Trinity assembly (see their high similarity to other sequences from toxic species). Right: Multiple sequence alignment of the mature peptide showing the repetitive motifs found using Multiple Em for Motif Elicitation (MEME).

Supplementary Figure S15. Maximum likelihood gene tree recovered from the analysis of 723 sodium channel toxin (NaTx) peptides recovered from our transcriptomic analyses and databases (UniProt and InterPro), plus two outgroups (inset). Multiple sequence alignment color-coded for the 376 peptides from the Cn2-like clade (highlighted in black on inset phylogeny). Mature peptide repetitive motifs found using Multiple Em for Motif Elicitation (MEME) locations as shown by colored bars. Highlighted in purple is the sole clade of iurid scorpion Cn2-like peptides.

1.3e-490

Supplementary Figure S16. Left: Pruned gene tree of the Cn2-like clade unique to *lurida*. Right: Multiple sequence alignment of the mature peptide showing the repetitive motifs found using Multiple Em for Motif Elicitation (MEME).

Supplementary Figure S17. Left: Pruned gene tree of the Cn2-like clade unique to the *Tityus* group, with emphasis on the genus *Centruroides*. Right: Multiple sequence alignment of the mature peptide showing the repetitive motifs found using Multiple Em for Motif Elicitation (MEME).

Supplementary Figure S18. Left: Pruned gene tree of the Cn2-like clade unique to the genus *Tityus*. Right: Multiple sequence alignment of the mature peptide showing the repetitive motifs found using Multiple Em for Motif Elicitation (MEME).

Supplementary Figure S19. Left: Comparative analysis of the consensus clades containing at least one peptide sequence with known function shown as function of their phylogenetic relationships. Right: Multiple sequence alignment of the consensus sequence (in black) and a representative sequence from that clade with known function. Green text: insect affinity; orange text: insect and mammal affinity; red text: mammal affinity.

Supplementary Figure S20. 95% credibility intervals from our mammal-active toxin origins (in red), compared to 95% credibility intervals of the four major mammal orders that include scorpion predators, as shown by Meredith et al. (2011) and Upham et al. (2019).

Table S1. List of 100 scorpion species and 20 outgroup taxa included in phylogenomic analyses.

Order	Family	Species	Datatype	Accession
Outgroup				
Amblypygi	Charinidae	<i>Sarax israelensis</i>	SRA	PRJNA649577
	Phrynichidae	<i>Damon variegatus</i>	SRA	SRR1145694
Araneae	Theraphosidae	<i>Aphonopelma hentzi</i>	SRA	SRX10000054-5
	Tetragnathidae	<i>Leucauge venusta</i>	SRA	SRR1145740
	Liphistiidae	<i>Liphistius malayanus</i>	SRA	SRR1145736
Opiliones	Acropsopilionidae	<i>Acropsopilio neozealandiae</i>	SRA	SRR5235984
	Caddidae	<i>Caddo agilis</i>	SRA	SAMN06309539
	Phalangidae	<i>Phalangium opilio</i>	SRA	SRX450969
	Sironidae	<i>Siro boyerae</i>	SRA	SRR1145699
	Taracidae	<i>Hesperonemastoma modestum</i>	SRA	SRR1145728
	Zalmoxidae	<i>Pachylicus acutus</i>	SRA	SRR1146670
Pseudoscorpiones	Chernetidae	<i>Hesperochernes</i> sp.	SRA	SRR1514877
	Feaellidae	<i>Feaella capensis</i>	SRA	SRR9331986
	Garypidae	<i>Synsphyronus apimelus</i>	SRA	SRR1145733
	Pseudotyranochthoniidae	<i>Pseudotyranochthonius</i> sp.	SRA	SRR9331998
Schizomida	Hubbardidae	<i>Stenochrus portoricensis</i>	SRA	SRR6997625
Thelyphonida	Thelyphonidae	<i>Mastigoproctus giganteus</i>	SRA	SRR1145698
Xiphosura	Limulidae	<i>Limulus polyphemus</i>	SRA	SRR1145732
	Limulidae	<i>Carcinoscorpius rotundicauda</i>	SRA	SRX503911
	Limulidae	<i>Tachypleus tridentatus</i>	SRA	SRX5091311
Ingroup				
Scorpiones	Belisariidae	<i>Belisarius xambeui</i>	SRA	SRR1721953
	Bothriuridae	<i>Bothriurus burmeisteri</i>	SRA	SRR1721670
		<i>Bothriurus coriaceus</i>	SRA	SRR6467511
		<i>Centromachetes</i> sp.	SRA	SRR6467879
		<i>Cercophonius sulcatus</i>	SRA	SRR6466561
		<i>Cercophonius squama</i>	SRA	SRR6470146
		<i>Cercophonius queenslandae</i>	SRA	SRR6470446
	Buthidae	<i>Androctonus amoreuxi</i>	SRA	SAMN09939440
		<i>Androctonus australis</i>	SRA	SRR1724216
		<i>Androctonus crassicauda</i>	SRA	SAMN23426188
		<i>Ananteris balzani</i>	SRA	SAMN09907396
		<i>Babycurus gigas</i>	SRA	SAMN23426189
		<i>Birulatus israelensis</i>	SRA	SAMN23426190
		<i>Buthacus</i> cf. <i>arenicola</i>	SRA	SAMN23426191
		<i>Buthus israelis</i>	SRA	SAMN23426192
		<i>Centruroides caribensis</i>	SRA	SAMN23426193
		<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	SRA	SRR1515193
		<i>Centruroides vittatus</i>	SRA	SRP035925
		<i>Compsobuthus levyi</i>	SRA	SAMN23426194
		<i>Compsobuthus schmiedknechti</i>	SRA	SAMN23426195
		<i>Compsobuthus</i> sp.	SRA	SAMN23426196
		<i>Grosphus grandidieri</i>	SRA	SAMN23426197
		<i>Heteroctenus garridoi</i>	SRA	SAMN23426198
		<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	SRA	SAMN23426199

	<i>Hottentotta trilineatus</i>	SRA	SRR1721800
	<i>Jaquajir agamemnon</i>	SRA	SAMN23426200
	<i>Jaquajir rochae</i>	SRA	SAMN23426201
	<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	SRA	SAMN23426202
	<i>Leiurus quinquestriatus</i>	SRA	SAMN23426203
	<i>Lychas variatus</i>	SRA	SAMN23426204
	<i>Orthochirus scrobiculosus</i>	SRA	SAMN23426205
	<i>Parabuthus transvaalicus</i>	SRA	SRR1721799
	<i>Physoctonus debilis</i>	SRA	SAMN23426206
	<i>Tityus costatus</i>	SRA	SAMN23426207
	<i>Tityus maranhensis</i>	SRA	SAMN23426208
	<i>Tityus smithi</i>	SRA	SAMN23426209
	<i>Troglorhopalurus lacrau</i>	SRA	SAMN23426210
	<i>Uroplectes olivaceus</i>	SRA	SAMN23426211
	<i>Uroplectes vittatus</i>	SRA	SAMN23426212
Caraboctonidae	<i>Caraboctonus keyserlingii</i>	SRA	SRR9053016
Chaeriliidae	<i>Chaerilus celebensis</i>	SRA	SRR1721804
Chactidae	<i>Anuroctonus phaiodactylus</i>	SRA	SRR1721879
	<i>Brotheas granulatus</i>	SRA	SRR1721887
Diplocentridae	<i>Diplocentrus diablo</i>	SRA	SRR1721672
	<i>Diplocentrus zacatecanus</i>	SRA	SAMN23438342
	<i>Kolotl magnus</i>	SRA	SRR7879236
	<i>Kolotl poncei</i>	SRA	SAMN23438343
	<i>Nebo hierichonticus</i>	SRA	SAMN23438341
Euscorpiidae	<i>Euscorpius italicus</i>	SRA	SRR1721892
	<i>Megacormus gertschi</i>	SRA	SRR3657526
	<i>Megacormus</i> sp.	SRA	SRR1767669
	<i>Plesiochactas dilutus</i>	SRA	SRR7250103
Hadruridae	<i>Hadrurus arizonensis</i>	SRA	SRR1721733
	<i>Hadrurus concolorous</i>	SRA	ERR3561754
	<i>Hadrurus spadix</i>	SRA	SRR4069278
	<i>Hoffmannihadrurus aztecus</i>	SRA	ERR3534794
Hormuridae	<i>Chiromachus ochropus</i>	SRA	SAMN23438348
	<i>Hadogenes</i> cf. <i>paucidens</i>	SRA	SAMN23438345
	<i>Hadogenes troglodytes</i>	SRA	SRR1721665
	<i>Hormiops davidovi</i>	SRA	SAMN23438338
	<i>Hormurus waigiensis</i>	SRA	SRR18036348
	<i>Iomachus politus</i>	SRA	SAMN23438344
	<i>Liocheles australasiae</i>	SRA	SRR1721664
	<i>Liocheles</i> sp.	SRA	SAMN23438340
	<i>Opisthacanthus</i> cf. <i>asper</i>	SRA	SAMN23438346
	<i>Opisthacanthus validus</i>	SRA	SAMN23438347
	<i>Opisthacanthus madagascariensis</i>	SRA	SRR1721668
	<i>Palaeocheloctonus pauliani</i>	SRA	SAMN23438349
Iuridae	<i>Iurus dekanum</i>	SRA	SRR1721734
Pseudochactidae	<i>Troglokhammouanus steineri</i>	SRA	SRR1721739
	<i>Vietbocap lao</i>	SRA	SRR1721740
Scorpiopidae	<i>Scorpiops</i> sp.	SRA	SRR1767662
Scorpionidae	<i>Opisthophthalmus</i> cf. <i>boehmi</i>	SRA	SAMN23438352

	<i>Opisthophthalmus cf. glabrifrons</i>	SRA	SAMN23438350
	<i>Opisthophthalmus cf. wahlbergii</i>	SRA	SAMN23438351
	<i>Pandinus imperator</i>	SRA	SRR1721600
	<i>Scorpio fuscus</i>	SRA	SRR7249741
Superstitioniidae	<i>Superstitionia donensis</i>	SRA	SRR1721951
Urodacidae	<i>Urodacus elongatus</i>	SRA	SRR7885472
	<i>Urodacus planimanus</i>	SRA	SAMN06114579
	<i>Urodacus yaschenkoi</i>	SRA	SRR1557168
Vaejovidae	<i>Chihuahuanus coahuilae</i>	SRA	SRR7439185
	<i>Konetontli acapulco</i>	SRA	SRR7422029
	<i>Konetontli chamelaensis</i>	SRA	SRR7427084
	<i>Kovarikia bogerti</i>	SRA	SRR8518584
	<i>Kuarapu purhepecha</i>	SRA	SRR7439043
	<i>Mesomexovis occidentalis</i>	SRA	SRR7439610
	<i>Mesomexovis aff. variegatus</i>	SRA	SRR7439652
	<i>Paravaejovis schwenkmeyeri</i>	SRA	SRR2653951
	<i>Paravaejovis spinigerus</i>	SRA	SRR1721954
	<i>Paruroctonus baergi</i>	SRA	SRR7443668
	<i>Pseudouroctonus apacheanus</i>	SRA	SRR8518585
	<i>Serradigitus gertschi</i>	SRA	ERR2843384
	<i>Smeringurus mesaensis</i>	SRA	SRR7473845
	<i>Smeringurus vachoni</i>	SRA	SRR7474136
	<i>Thorellius intrepidus</i>	SRA	SRR7427141
	<i>Uroctonites huachuca</i>	SRA	SRR8518582
	<i>Vaejovis cashi</i>	SRA	SRR8518583
	<i>Vaejovis mexicanus</i>	SRA	SRR7421527
<i>incertae sedis</i>	<i>Uroctonus mordax</i>	SRA	SRR8518581

Table S2. Collecting localities of newly sequenced scorpions.

Species	Locality / Region of origin	Latitude	Longitude	Date	Collector
<i>Ananteris balzani</i>	Brazil: São Paulo State, Aguas de Sant Bárbara	-22.84	-49.35	V.2017	R. Pinto da Rocha
<i>Androctonus amoreuxi</i>	Israel: Haluza Sand dunes, East of Be'er Milka	30.93	34.41	31.vii.2017	C. Shlomo
<i>Androctonus crassicauda</i>	Israel: Entrance to Susita National Park, hand collecting and black-lighting at night	35.66362	32.77397		E. Gavish-Regev, S. Aharon, I. Armiach, J.A. Ballesteros, G. Gainett, P. Sharma
<i>Babycurus gigas</i>	USA: North Carolina	n/a	n/a	iv.2018	Captive bred (source colony B. Myers)
<i>Birulatus israelensis</i>	Israel: Mehola, Giv'at Sal'it Outside trail	32.36	35.51	7.v.2018	Y. Zvik
<i>Buthacus cf. arenicola</i>	Egypt: Senai, El Maghara	n/a	n/a	5/28/18	M. Kamel
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	Israel: Haluqim Ridge, West of Midreshet Ben-Gurion	30.85	34.76	16.VI.2017	E. Gavish-Regev & P. Sharma
<i>Centruroides caribensis</i>	USA: North Carolina	n/a	n/a	1.iii.2017	Captive bred (source colony B. Myers)
<i>Chiromachus ochropus</i>	Seychelles: Fregate Island	n/a	n/a	16.vii.2008	L. Monod
<i>Compsobuthus levyi</i>	Israel: Qanna'im Wadi near Arad	31.30	35.31	22.IX.2017	Y. Zvik
<i>Compsobuthus schmiedknechti</i>	Israel: Nahal Ktalav	31.73	35.07	19.VI.2017	E. Gavish-Regev & P. Sharma
<i>Compsobuthus sp.</i>	Israel: north to Rotem	32.34	35.52	4.vii.2016	Y. Zvik
<i>Diplocentrus zacatecanus</i>	Mexico: Zacatecas: Municipio Genaro Codina, 3 km SW de Genaro Codina	22.47	-102.48	2.ii.2017	P. Cushing, H. Carmona, E. González-Santillán
<i>Grosphus grandidieri</i>	Madagascar: ex-Province de Toamasina, Région Atsinana, Réserve Nat. Intégrale de Betampona	-17.91	49.18	11/16/15	S. Goodman
<i>Hadogenes cf. paucidens</i>	Tanzania	n/a	n/a	n/a	Captive bred (source colony L. Monod)
<i>Heteroctenus garridoi</i>	Cuba	n/a	n/a	n/a	Captive bred (source colony P. Sharma)
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	Cuba	n/a	n/a	n/a	Captive bred (source colony B. Myers)
<i>Hormiops davidovi</i>	Vietnam: Con Son Island	n/a	n/a	8.i.2012	L. Monod
<i>Hormurus waigiensis</i>	Indonesia: Sulawesi Tengah, Pulau Peleng	n/a	n/a	16.iv.2013	L. Monod
<i>Iomachus politus</i>	Tanzania	n/a	n/a	n/a	Captive bred (source colony L. Monod)
<i>Jaquajir agamemnon</i>	Brazil: Piauí State, Castelo do Piauí	-5.32	-41.55	23.iii.2018	R. Pinto da Rocha
<i>Jaquajir rochae</i>	Brazil: Piauí State, Castelo do Piauí	-5.32	-41.55	23.iii.2018	R. Pinto da Rocha
<i>Kolotl poncei</i>	Mexico: Michoacan, Minicipio la Huacana, km 17 carretera Zicuiaran-Churumuco	18.81	-101.92	16.v.2015	E. Oliveros, J. Ponce-Saavedra, A. Quijano, J. Maldonado, E. González-Santillán
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>		30.99	34.89	5.viii.2016	Y. Zvik

<i>Leiurus quinquestriatus</i>	Israel: 100 meter north to Yeruham Lake , on ridge Egypt	n/a	n/a	n/a	Captive bred (source colony E. Gavish-Regev)
<i>Liocheles</i> sp.	Thailand: Prachuap Khiri Khan Province	n/a	n/a	25.xii.2012	L. Monod
<i>Lychas variatus</i>	Australia: Queensland	21.13297	148.49246	27.v.2015	P. Sharma
<i>Nebo hierichonticus</i>	Israel:	n/a	n/a	n/a	Captive bred (source colony E. Gavish-Regev)
<i>Opisthacanthus</i> cf. <i>asper</i>	Tanzania	n/a	n/a	n/a	Captive bred (source colony L. Monod)
<i>Opisthacanthus validus</i>	South Africa	n/a	n/a	n/a	Captive bred (source colony L. Monod)
<i>Opisthophthalmus</i> cf. <i>boehmi</i>	Tanzania	n/a	n/a	n/a	Captive bred (source colony L. Monod)
<i>Opisthophthalmus</i> cf. <i>glabrifrons</i>	Mozambic	n/a	n/a	n/a	Captive bred (source colony L. Monod)
<i>Opisthophthalmus</i> cf. <i>wahlbergii</i>	Mozambic	n/a	n/a	n/a	Captive bred (source colony L. Monod)
<i>Orthochirus scrobiculosus</i>	Israel: Haluqim Ridge, West of Midreshet Ben-Gurion	30.85	34.76	16.VI.2017	E. Gavish-Regev & P. Sharma
<i>Palaeocheloctonus pauliani</i>	Madagascar	n/a	n/a	n/a	Captive bred (source colony L. Monod)
<i>Physoctonus debilis</i>	Brazil: Piaui State, Castelo do Piauí	-5.32	-41.55	23.iii.2018	R. Pinto da Rocha
<i>Tityus costatus</i>	Brazil: São Paulo State	n/a	n/a	2017	R. Pinto da Rocha
<i>Tityus maranhensis</i>	Brazil: Ceará State, Ubajara (Pousada Sítio do Alemão)	-3.73	-40.90	24.iii.2018	R. Pinto da Rocha
<i>Tityus smithi</i>	USA: North Carolina	n/a	n/a	n/a	Captive bred (source colony B. Myers)
<i>Troglorhopalurus lacrau</i>	Brazil: Bahia State, Itaeté (Lapa do Bode)	-12.98	-40.97	22.iii.2017	R. Pinto da Rocha
<i>Uroplectes olivaceus</i>	USA: North Carolina	n/a	n/a	n/a	Captive bred (source colony B. Myers)
<i>Uroplectes vittatus</i>	USA: North Carolina	n/a	n/a	n/a	Captive bred (source colony B. Myers)

Table S3. Readouts and accession data for 42 scorpion species newly sequenced in this study.

	Species	Reads	Contigs	Method
BUTHOIDEA				
Buthidae	<i>Androctonus amoreuxi</i>	19078891	56289	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Androctonus crassicauda</i>	22416824	23683	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Ananteris balzani</i>	22362527	83351	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Babycurus gigas</i>	16376118	5913	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Birulatus israelensis</i>	50794420	71390	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Buthacus cf. arenicola</i>	19804050	65727	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Buthus israelis</i>	62601743	31901	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Centruroides caribensis</i>	16971304	77404	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Compsobuthus levyi</i>	18633893	73168	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Compsobuthus schmiedknechti</i>	76433324	59310	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Compsobuthus sp.</i>	61356146	55775	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Grosphus grandidieri</i>	33078770	68375	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Heteroctenus garridoi</i>	25401187	80482	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	30459300	167545	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Jaquajir agamemnon</i>	19088930	48581	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Jaquajir rochae</i>	14969285	40854	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	18235433	50196	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Leiurus quinquestriatus</i>	17163687	63331	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Lychas variatus</i>	16471150	84008	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Orthochirus scrobiculosus</i>	31849129	32859	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Physoctonus debilis</i>	12895814	12062	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Tityus costatus</i>	17843661	69201	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Tityus maranhensis</i>	16247484	62184	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Tityus smithi</i>	19198142	78192	HiSeq 2 X 150

	<i>Troglorhopalurus lacrau</i>	16104040	65928	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Uroplectes olivaceus</i>	19657025	71864	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Uroplectes vittatus</i>	19980384	245104	HiSeq 2 X 150
SCORPIONOIDEA				
Diplocentridae	<i>Diplocentrus zacatecanus</i>	64264547	141792	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Kolotl poncei</i>	25294080	105290	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Nebo hierichonticus</i>	40511893	647989	HiSeq 2 X 150
Hormuridae	<i>Chiromachus ochropus</i>	25719159	249450	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Hadogenes paucidens</i>	26367367	140326	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Hormiops davidovi</i>	27660036	378177	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Hormurus waigiensis</i>	20560984	287004	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Iomachus politus</i>	23055924	300022	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Liocheles</i> sp.	18600474	86885	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Opisthacanthus</i> cf. <i>asper</i>	24099159	513757	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Opisthacanthus validus</i>	16652215	252340	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Palaeocheloctonus pauliani</i>	9955624	267572	HiSeq 2 X 150
Scorpionidae	<i>Opisthophthalmus</i> cf. <i>boehmi</i>	40823006	60020	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Opisthophthalmus</i> cf. <i>glabrifrons</i>	34221314	305201	HiSeq 2 X 150
	<i>Opisthophthalmus</i> cf. <i>wahlbergii</i>	22341990	265140	HiSeq 2 X 150

Table S4. Accession data for 21 scorpion species, plus other Sanger-sequenced datasets, added to phylogenetic analyses to tests generic groupings within Buthidae (“M2plus”).

	Species	Datatype	Accession	18S rRNA	COI	16S rRNA
BUTHOIDEA						
Buthidae	<i>Anateris balzani</i>	SRA	see Table S1	From transcriptome	KY674491	KY674448
	<i>Babycurus gigas</i>	SRA	see Table S1	From transcriptome	Not available	Not available
	<i>Androctonus amoreuxi</i>	SRA	see Table S1	From transcriptome	KJ538492	AY226175
	<i>Androctonus australis</i>	SRA	see Table S1	From transcriptome	AF370829	KJ538473
	<i>Androctonus crassicauda</i>	SRA	see Table S1	From transcriptome	HM567333	FJ217735
	<i>Androctonus mauritanicus</i>	SRA	PRJNA556947	From transcriptome	Not available	Not available
	<i>Apistobuthus pterygocercus</i>	Sanger	-	Not available	Not available	AY226178
	<i>Birulatus israelensis</i>	SRA	see Table S1	From transcriptome	Not available	Not available
	<i>Buthacus cf. arenicola</i>	SRA	see Table S1	From transcriptome	Not available	Not available
	<i>Buthus israelensis</i>	SRA	see Table S1	From transcriptome	Not available	Not available
	<i>Compsobuthus levyi</i>	SRA	see Table S1	From transcriptome	Not available	Not available
	<i>Hottentotta gentilli</i>	SRA	PRJNA556947	From transcriptome	JF820093	JQ514227
	<i>Hottentotta trilineatus</i>	SRA	see Table S1	From transcriptome	Not available	Not available
	<i>Kraepelinia palpator</i>	Sanger	-	Not available	Not available	AY226181
	<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	SRA	see Table S1	From transcriptome	Not available	Not available
	<i>Leiurus quinquestriatus</i>	SRA	see Table S1	From transcriptome	JQ514258	AY226174
	<i>Liobuthus kessleri</i>	Sanger	-	Not available	MN071133	MN071126
	<i>Mesobuthus gibbosus</i>	EST	[1]	Not available	DQ310884	DQ310847
	<i>Meosbuthus martensii</i>	Genome	GCA_000484575.1	AB008465	JF700146	Not available
	<i>Orthochirus scrobiculosus</i>	SRA	see Table S1	From transcriptome	Not available	Not available
	<i>Vachoniolus globimanus</i>	Sanger	-	Not available	Not available	AY226179
	<i>Australobuthus xerolimniorum</i>	SRA	SRR870659	Not available	Not available	Not available
	<i>Isometroides vescus</i>	SRA	SRR870661	Not available	Not available	Not available

	<i>Lychas buchardi</i>	SRA	SRR870662	Not available	Not available	Not available
	<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	Sanger	-	JN018270	JN018153	AF370855
	<i>Lychas variatus</i>	SRA	see Table S1	From transcriptome	Not available	Not available
	<i>Charmus</i> sp.	Sanger	-	Not available	MF422296	Not available
	<i>Grosphus flavopiceus</i>	Sanger	-	JN018269	JN018152	JQ514238
	<i>Grosphus grandidieri</i>	SRA	see Table S1	From transcriptome	Not available	Not available
	<i>Parabuthus laevifrons</i>	Sanger	-	JN018271	JN018154	Not available
	<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	SRA	SRX3189905	AF062948	MK479177	Not available
	<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	SRA	SRX708114	JN018272	JN018155	AY586781
Chaeriliidae	<i>Chaerilus julietteae</i>	Sanger	-	JN018280	JN018163	Not available
	<i>Chaerilus</i> sp.	Sanger	-	JN018279	JN018162	Not available
IUROIDEA						
Iuridae	<i>Protoiurus kraepelini</i>	SRA	PRJNA556947	Not available	Not available	Not available

[1] Diego-García, E., Caliskan, F. & Tytgat, J. 2014. The Mediterranean scorpion *Mesobuthus gibbosus* (Scorpiones, Buthidae): transcriptome analysis and organization of the genome encoding chlorotoxin-like peptides. BMC Genomics 15, 295

Table S5. Fossil calibrations used in molecular dating analyses. Ages in millions of years.

Node calibrated	Fossil	Minimum age	Maximum age	Reference
Root		none	550	Numerous
Opiliones (stem)	<i>Eophalangium sheari</i>	411	none	Garwood et al. 2014
Eupnoi (Caddo + Phalangium)	<i>Ameticos scolos</i>	305	none	Garwood et al. 2011
Dyspnoi (Acropsopilio + Hesperonemastoma)	<i>Macroglyion cronus</i>	305	none	Garwood et al. 2011
Araneae (stem)	<i>Attercopus fimbriunguis</i>	386	none	Selden et al. 2008, Huang et al. 2018
Amblypygi (stem)	<i>Graeophonus anglicus</i> , <i>Graeophonus carbonarius</i>	312	none	Pocock 1911
Thelyphonida (stem)	<i>Prothelyphonus naufraga</i>	319	none	Brauckmann and Kock 1983
Liphistiidae	<i>Palaeothele montceauensis</i>	305	none	Selden 1996
Xiphosura (stem)	<i>Lunataspis aurora</i>	445	none	Rudkin et al. 2008
Pseudoscorpiones (stem)	<i>Dracochela deprehendor</i>	392	none	Schawaller et al. 1991
Scorpiones (stem)	<i>Dolichophonus loudenensis</i> , <i>Eramoscorpilus brucensis</i>	435.15	514	Laurie 1899
Scorpiones (crown)	<i>Protoischnurus axelrodurum</i> , <i>Compsoscorpilus buthiformis</i>	112.6	313.7	de Carvalho and Lourenço 2001; Menon 2007
Iurida (stem)	<i>Protoischnurus axelrodurum</i> , <i>Compsoscorpilus buthiformis</i>	112.6	313.7	de Carvalho and Lourenço 2001; Menon 2007
Chaerilidae (stem)	<i>Electrochaerilus buckleyi</i>	98.17	313.7	Santiago-Blay 2004; Soleglad et al. 2004a
Buthoidea (crown)	<i>Uintascorpio halandrasii</i>	49.26	313.7	Perry 1995, Soleglad et al. 2004b
Scorpionioidea (crown)	<i>Compsoscorpilus buthiformis</i>	112.6	313.7	Pointon et al. 2012

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Table S6. Sequences of scorpion toxins retrieved from UniProt. Asterisks indicate peptides with known mammal affinity, with associated references.

Species	Class	UniProt accession number	References for mammal-active peptides
<i>Opisthacanthus cayaporum</i>	DDH	C5J894	
<i>Hemiscorpius lepturus</i>	DDH	A0A1L4BJ56	
<i>Liocheles australasiae</i>	DDH	PODJ08	
<i>Urodacus manicatus</i>	DDH	T1DMR4	
<i>Urodacus manicatus</i>	DDH	T1DEJ5	
<i>Urodacus manicatus</i>	DDH	T1DPA2	
<i>Opisthophthalmus carinatus</i>	Calcin	P60253	
<i>Opisthophthalmus carinatus</i>	Calcin	P60252	
<i>Pandinus imperator</i>	Calcin	P59868	
<i>Hemiscorpius lepturus</i>	Calcin	A0A1L4BJ42	
<i>Scorpio maurus</i>	Calcin	P60254	
<i>Megacormus gertschi</i>	Calcin	A0A224X3Z6	
<i>Megacormus gertschi</i>	Calcin	A0A224X3X5	
<i>Superstitionia donensis</i>	Calcin	A0A1V1WBN6	
<i>Superstitionia donensis</i>	Calcin	A0A1V1WBN1	
<i>Hoffmanniadrurus gertschi</i>	Calcin	B8QG00	
<i>Hadrurus spadix</i>	Calcin	JAV48253	
<i>Vaejovis mexicanus</i>	Calcin	PODPT1	
<i>Thorellius intrepidus</i>	Calcin	PODM30	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	A0A146CIP8	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	A0A143MGK4	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	A0A146CIP9	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	P15220	
<i>Mesobuthus gibbosus</i>	CITx	A0A023UGK1	
<i>Mesobuthus gibbosus</i>	CITx	A0A023UH07	
<i>Mesobuthus gibbosus</i>	CITx	A0A023UFA0	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	P60268	
<i>Leiurus quinquestriatus</i>	CITx	P45639	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	A0A0D4CYV3	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	CITx	Q9BJW4	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	CITx	Q9UAD0	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	A0A146CJD6	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	A0A146CJF8	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	A0A0D4CZV2	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	F1DI80	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	P60269	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	P60270	
<i>Androctonus australis</i>	CITx	P86436	

<i>Buthus israelis</i>	CITx	B8XH25
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	CITx	B8XH27
<i>Hottentotta tamulus</i>	CITx	P81761
<i>Hottentotta tamulus</i>	CITx	P83400
<i>Hottentotta judaicus</i>	CITx	F1CIY7
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	P15222
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	P86401
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	E4VP45
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	E4VP46
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	R4H559
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	P86402
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	CITx	R4H5A4
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	CITx	P55966
<i>Hottentotta tamulus</i>	CITx	P15229
<i>Parabuthus schlechteri</i>	CITx	P60271
<i>Odontobuthus doriae</i>	CITx	A0A0U3YCU6
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	CITx	P85066
<i>Androctonus mauritanicus</i>	CITx	P01498
<i>Hottentotta tamulus</i>	CITx	P59887
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	CITx	B8XH23
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	KTx	P0CI88
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	KTx	P0DJL0
<i>Mesobuthus gibbosus</i>	KTx	A0A059UJH5
<i>Hottentotta conspersus</i>	KTx	JZ8220909
<i>Hottentotta judaicus</i>	KTx	F1CIZ6
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	Q8I6X9
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	KTx	P0C175
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	P86399
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	P86399
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	KTx	A0A0K0LBY9
<i>Buthus occitanus</i>	KTx	B8XH22
<i>Androctonus australisS</i>	KTx	LKTx
<i>Hoffmannihadrurus gertschi</i>	KTx	Q0GY40
<i>Heterometrus laoticus</i>	KTx	P0DJ41
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	A0A088D9T9
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	A7KJJ7
<i>Buthus tunetanus</i>	KTx	COHJQ2
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	A0A088DAE2
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	P83407
<i>Centruroides tecomanus</i>	KTx	COHJW2

<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	KTx	D9U2B0
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	KTx	A0A0U1SA71
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	KTx	A0A0U1S616
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	KTx	A0A0U1SK86
<i>Chaerilus tricostatus</i>	KTx	P0DJO5
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	KTx	P0CI47
<i>Isometroides vescus</i>	KTx	T1DMS1
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	KTx	A0A0U1SSR1
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	KTx	B8XH44
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	KTx	A0A0U1TYB8
<i>Mesobuthus gibbosus</i>	KTx	A0A059UEE4
<i>Mesobuthus gibbosus</i>	KTx	A0A059UHK0
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	KTx	A0A1E1WVQ0
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	KTx	A0A1E1WVW2
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	KTx	P84777
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	KTx	D9U2A8
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	KTx	B8XH38
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	A0A088D9R3
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	KTx	B8XH43
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	Q86BX0
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	KTx	B8XH37
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	A0A088DB08
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	Q8I0L5
<i>Androctonus amoreuxi</i>	KTx	Q5K0E0
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	A0A143MGR2
<i>Androctonus australis</i>	KTx	Q86SD8
<i>Androctonus australis</i>	KTx	Q867F4
<i>Androctonus australis</i>	KTx	P60233
<i>Androctonus mauritanicus</i>	KTx	P60208
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	KTx	A0A0U1TYC6
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	KTx	P0CJ24
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	KTx	A0A0U1S4N0
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	KTx	A0A0U1TZ20
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	KTx	A0A0U1SCI3
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	KTx	A0A0U1S505
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	KTx	P0CH12
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	KTx	A0A0U1TZ12
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	KTx	P0CI48
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	A0A088D9S3
<i>Androctonus mauritanicus</i>	KTx	P31719

<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	Q9TVX3
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	KTx	P16341
<i>Hottentotta tamulus</i>	KTx	P59869
<i>Hottentotta tamulus</i>	KTx	P59870
<i>Orthochirus scrobiculosus</i>	KTx	P55896
<i>Buthus occitanus paris</i>	KTx	P0DL44
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	KTx	B8XH29
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	KTx	POC908
<i>Hottentotta tamulus</i>	KTx	P59886
<i>Odontobuthus doriae</i>	KTx	A0A0U4FP89
<i>Odontobuthus doriae</i>	KTx	POC909
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	KTx	B8XH48
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	KTx	P46110
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	KTx	P46111
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	KTx	P46112
<i>Androctonus mauritanicus</i>	KTx	P24662
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	KTx	A0A0K0LBX5
<i>Androctonus amoreuxi</i>	KTx	POC8R1
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	P86396
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	C0HJQ6
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	Q9NII7
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	A0A088D9R0
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	KTx	A0A0K0LBX7
<i>Buthus tunetanus</i>	KTx	P59290
<i>Androctonus australis</i>	KTx	P45696
<i>Mesobuthus gibbosus</i>	KTx	K7XFK5
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	A0A088D9R9
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	A0A088DB48
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	C0HJQ4
<i>Centruroides suffusus</i>	KTx	P85529
<i>Centruroides tecomanus</i>	KTx	C0HJW1
<i>Centruroides elegans</i>	KTx	POC163
<i>Centruroides limpidus</i>	KTx	P45629
<i>Centruroides elegans</i>	KTx	POC162
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	KTx	P08815
<i>Centruroides elegans</i>	KTx	POC161
<i>Centruroides tecomanus</i>	KTx	C0HJW6
<i>Centruroides elegans</i>	KTx	POC164
<i>Centruroides tecomanus</i>	KTx	C0HJW5
<i>Centruroides elegans</i>	KTx	POC165

<i>Centruroides limpidus</i>	KTx	PODL70
<i>Centruroides limpidus</i>	KTx	P45630
<i>Centruroides limbatus</i>	KTx	P59847
<i>Centruroides limbatus</i>	KTx	P59850
<i>Centruroides margaritatus</i>	KTx	P40755
<i>Centruroides limbatus</i>	KTx	P59849
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	KTx	COHJT0
<i>Heteroctenus garridoi</i>	KTx	PODL43
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	KTx	A0A2I9LNQ2
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	KTx	A0A2I9LNP3
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	KTx	A0A2I9LNQ1
<i>Centruroides limbatus</i>	KTx	P59848
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	KTx	A0A2I9LNQ6
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	KTx	A0A2I9LNP1
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	KTx	Q9TXD1
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	KTx	A0A2I9LNP9
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	KTx	A0A1E1WWJ8
<i>Tityus bahiensis</i>	KTx	A0A0C9S0L0
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	KTx	P56219
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	KTx	P59925
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	KTx	P60210
<i>Parabuthus transvaalicus</i>	KTx	P83112
<i>Tityus stigmurus</i>	KTx	P0CB56
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	KTx	P46114
<i>Tityus stigmurus</i>	KTx	P0DPT4
<i>Tityus bahiensis</i>	KTx	A0A0C9QKU6
<i>Tityus costatus</i>	KTx	Q5G8B6
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	KTx	A0A218QXG2
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	KTx	A0A218QX22
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	KTx	A0A218QWZ7
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	KTx	A0A218QWZ8
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	KTx	A0A218QXC2
<i>Tityus costatus</i>	KTx	P0C185
<i>Tityus bahiensis</i>	KTx	A0A0C9S3A0
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	KTx	A0A218QXB7
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	KTx	P59936
<i>Tityus trivittatus</i>	KTx	P0C168
<i>Tityus stigmurus</i>	KTx	P0C8L1
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	P59938
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	A0A088DAE4

<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	Q9BKB7
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	V9LLY8
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	A0A143Q3Q3
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	H2ER23
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	Q9NII6
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	A0RZD1
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	C0HJQ7
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	C0HJQ8
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	H2ETQ6
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	A0A088DAD7
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	H2ER22
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	Q1EFP8
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	Q9NII5
<i>Hottentotta judaicus</i>	KTx	F1CJ83
<i>Hottentotta tamulus</i>	KTx	P24663
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	KTx	POC182
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	KTx	C0HJS9
<i>Centruroides limbatus</i>	KTx	POC167
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	KTx	P45628
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	KTx	P59943
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	KTx	P59944
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	KTx	P13487
<i>Buthus occitanus paris</i>	KTx	P0DL45
<i>Buthus occitanus paris</i>	KTx	P0DL46
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	KTx	A0A0K0LCI3
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	KTx	B8XH42
<i>Mesobuthus gibbosus</i>	KTx	B3EWY1
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	A0A088DAC3
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	D3JXM1
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	A0A088D9P9
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	KTx	A0A088DAY7
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	KTx	P45660
<i>Hottentotta tamulus</i>	KTx	POC173
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	Q8MQL0
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	Q9NBG9
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	KTx	V9LLQ7
<i>Pandinus cavimanus</i>	KTx	H2CYS1
<i>Hemiscorpius lepturus</i>	KTx	A0A1L4BJ36
<i>Hemiscorpius lepturus</i>	KTx	A0A1L4BJ31
<i>Opisthacanthus madagascariensis</i>	KTx	POC194

<i>Megacormus gertschi</i>	KTx	A0A224XGD9
<i>Anuroctonus phaiodactylus</i>	KTx	POC166
<i>Superstitionia donensis</i>	KTx	A0A1V1WBW9
<i>Superstitionia donensis</i>	KTx	A0A1V1WBN8
<i>Superstitionia donensis</i>	KTx	A0A1V1WBP1
<i>Hadogenes troglodytes</i>	KTx	A0A1B3IJ17
<i>Scorpiops tibetanus</i>	KTx	P0DP36
<i>Vaejovis smithi</i>	KTx	P0DJ31
<i>Megacormus gertschi</i>	KTx	A0A224X3K8
<i>Vaejovis smithi</i>	KTx	P0DJ32
<i>Hadrurus spadix</i>	KTx	A0A1W7RB29
<i>Hadrurus spadix</i>	KTx	A0A1W7RB38
<i>Hadrurus spadix</i>	KTx	A0A1W7RB23
<i>Hoffmannihadrurus gertschi</i>	KTx	P84864
<i>Hadrurus spadix</i>	KTx	A0A1W7RB41
<i>Hadrurus spadix</i>	KTx	A0A1W7RB24
<i>Hadrurus spadix</i>	KTx	A0A1W7RB16
<i>Hadrurus spadix</i>	KTx	A0A1W7RB43
<i>Opisthacanthus cayaporum</i>	KTx	P86115
<i>Opisthacanthus cayaporum</i>	KTx	P86116
<i>Urodacus yaschenkoi</i>	KTx	A0A0A0PI37
<i>Pandinus imperator</i>	KTx	P55927
<i>Pandinus imperator</i>	KTx	P55928
<i>Urodacus yaschenkoi</i>	KTx	A0A0A0PP73
<i>Urodacus yaschenkoi</i>	KTx	P0DL37
<i>Urodacus yaschenkoi</i>	KTx	A0A0A0PK31
<i>Urodacus yaschenkoi</i>	KTx	A0A0A0PJX6
<i>Urodacus yaschenkoi</i>	KTx	A0A0A0PTG7
<i>Opisthophthalmus carinatus</i>	KTx	Q6XLL5
<i>Opisthophthalmus carinatus</i>	KTx	Q6XLL6
<i>Opisthophthalmus carinatus</i>	KTx	Q6XLL7
<i>Opisthophthalmus carinatus</i>	KTx	Q6XLL8
<i>Opisthophthalmus carinatus</i>	KTx	Q6XLL9
<i>Heterometrus laoticus</i>	KTx	I6NXS5
<i>Heterometrus spinifer</i>	KTx	P59867
<i>Heterometrus laoticus</i>	KTx	I6NWV2
<i>Opisthacanthus cayaporum</i>	KTx	P86106
<i>Hemiscorpius lepturus</i>	KTx	A0A1L4BJ37
<i>Hemiscorpius lepturus</i>	KTx	P85528
<i>Scorpio palmatus</i>	KTx	P80719

<i>Pandinus imperator</i>	KTx	P58490
<i>Heterometrus spinifer</i>	KTx	P84094
<i>Pandinus imperator</i>	KTx	Q10726
<i>Pandinus imperator</i>	KTx	P58498
<i>Megacormus gertschi</i>	KTx	A0A224XBG0
<i>Superstitionia donensis</i>	KTx	A0A1V1WBN3
<i>Superstitionia donensis</i>	KTx	A0A1V1WC28
<i>Superstitionia donensis</i>	KTx	A0A1V1WBQ0
<i>Superstitionia donensis</i>	KTx	A0A1V1WC84
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	P0DJ46
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	P0DJ45
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	P0DJ48
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	P0DJ49
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	P0DJ47
<i>Hoffmannihadrurus gertschi</i>	NaTx	POC8W3
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	P0DJ50
<i>Hottentotta tamulus</i>	NaTx	P60277
<i>Hottentotta judaicus</i>	NaTx	F1CJ92
<i>Odontobuthus doriae</i>	NaTx	P84646
<i>Buthacus macrocentrus</i>	NaTx	P0DJH8
<i>Leiurus quinquestriatus</i>	NaTx	P01489
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	P83644
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XGX9
<i>Hottentotta tamulus</i>	NaTx	P84614
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LBX2
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	P86403
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	D8UWD8
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	A0A146CJ08
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	P09982
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XGY7
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XGY1
<i>Hottentotta judaicus</i>	NaTx	D5HR55
<i>Hottentotta judaicus</i>	NaTx	F0V3W1
<i>Hottentotta judaicus</i>	NaTx	Q56TT9
<i>Hottentotta judaicus</i>	NaTx	F1CJ53
<i>Hottentotta judaicus</i>	NaTx	F0V3W0
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	A0A146CJC0
<i>Hottentotta judaicus</i>	NaTx	F1CJ49
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	PODMH9
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	P56569

<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	P59853	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	P54135	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q86BW9	
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	D5HR49	
<i>Androctonus mauritanicus</i>	NaTx	Q2YHM1	
<i>Androctonus amoreuxi</i>	NaTx	Q86SE0	
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XGY3	
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XGZ6	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	A0A0B5GD34	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	G4V3T9	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	A0F0C1	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q9NJC7	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q9GNG8	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q49S27	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q9GYX2	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q95P69	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q1EG63	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q4TUA4	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q9GUA7	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	A0A143FHE4	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	P82815	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	D8UWD3	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	P86408*	[1]
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	P01490	
<i>Androctonus australis</i>	NaTx	Q9BLM4	
<i>Androctonus mauritanicus</i>	NaTx	P01482	
<i>Leiurus quinquestriatus</i>	NaTx	P01481*	[2-5]
<i>Androctonus crassicauda</i>	NaTx	M1JMR8	
<i>Buthus tunetanus</i>	NaTx	P01486	
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	D5HR48	
<i>Androctonus mauritanicus</i>	NaTx	Q7YXD3*	[2] [4]
<i>Androctonus crassicauda</i>	NaTx	D5HR52	
<i>Androctonus crassicauda</i>	NaTx	D5HR51	
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XGY5	
<i>Buthus tunetanus</i>	NaTx	P01485*	[6]
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	D5HR56	
<i>Androctonus australis</i>	NaTx	P01484*	[2-5]
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	P59355*	[7-8]
<i>Odontobuthus doriae</i>	NaTx	A0A4D6P363	
<i>Buthus occitanus mardochei</i>	NaTx	P60258	

<i>Buthus occitanus mardochei</i>	NaTx	P60256
<i>Buthus occitanus mardochei</i>	NaTx	P60255
<i>Buthus occitanus mardochei</i>	NaTx	P60259
<i>Odontobuthus doriae</i>	NaTx	A0A0U4RZC4
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LBU4
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q9GQW3
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q1EG64
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q1EG65
<i>Hadrurus spadix</i>	NaTx	A0A1W7R9B4
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XGY0
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XGY9
<i>Androctonus crassicauda</i>	NaTx	M1JB54
<i>Androctonus garzonii</i>	NaTx	E6ZB76
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LBW7
<i>Androctonus mauritanicus</i>	NaTx	D5HR54
<i>Androctonus amoreuxi</i>	NaTx	Q86SD9
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XGZ5
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XGY8
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XGZ2
<i>Buthus tunetanus</i>	NaTx	Q17254
<i>Odontobuthus doriae</i>	NaTx	A0A0U4Q545
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	D5HR57
<i>Buthus occitanus mardochei</i>	NaTx	P13488
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	P56678
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	P59357
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	E7CZZ1
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	A0A146CJ90
<i>Buthus tunetanus</i>	NaTx	P01483
<i>Buthus occitanus mardochei</i>	NaTx	P59896
<i>Buthus tunetanus</i>	NaTx	P01488
<i>Buthus occitanus mardochei</i>	NaTx	P59354
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	P09981
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	G4WFQ2
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	E7CZY9
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	E7CZZ0
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	D8UWD5
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	D8UWD6
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	E7D082
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	P86404
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	P86405

<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	P59854	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q9NJC5	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q9GQV6	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	P45697	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	P59360	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	P58488	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q6IZE0	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	P15227	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	P45698	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q9N682	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	B6A8R9	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	B6A8S0	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1TXT4	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	O61705	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q6IZE1	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	P58328	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q9NJC8	
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XGY4	
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XGZ4	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	E7CAU3	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q9NJC4	
<i>Buthus occitanus mardochei</i>	NaTx	P60257	
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XGY6	
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XGZ0	
<i>Buthus tunetanus</i>	NaTx	P55902	
<i>Androctonus australis</i>	NaTx	Q9BLM3	
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	P17728	
<i>Leiurus quinquestriatus</i>	NaTx	P01487	
<i>Buthus tunetanus</i>	NaTx	P04099	
<i>Oscrobiculosus</i>	NaTx	P15224	
<i>Androctonus crassicauda</i>	NaTx	D5HR50	
<i>Androctonus australis</i>	NaTx	P01479*	[9]
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LBW8	
<i>Androctonus crassicauda</i>	NaTx	M1JBC0	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	P0CI55	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1SBV9	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	D9U298	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	P0CI54	
<i>Androctonus crassicauda</i>	NaTx	M1J7U4	
<i>Androctonus crassicauda</i>	NaTx	E7BLC7	

<i>Androctonus australis</i>	NaTx	P80950	
<i>Androctonus australis</i>	NaTx	P56743	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LPB3	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LPC3	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LPB4	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LPC0	
<i>Superstitionia donensis</i>	NaTx	A0A1V1WBP9	
<i>Superstitionia donensis</i>	NaTx	A0A1V1WC92	
<i>Superstitionia donensis</i>	NaTx	A0A1V1WBQ9	
<i>Superstitionia donensis</i>	NaTx	A0A1V1WBQ8	
<i>Aphaiodactylus</i>	NaTx	Q5MJP5	
<i>Urodacus manicatus</i>	NaTx	T1DPA4	
<i>Cercophonius squama</i>	NaTx	T1DEJ4	
<i>Cercophonius squama</i>	NaTx	T1DMR2	
<i>Megacormus gertschi</i>	NaTx	A0A224X3Y8	
<i>Superstitionia donensis</i>	NaTx	A0A1V1WBR1	
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	NaTx	A0A218QXD4	
<i>Centruroides exilicauda</i>	NaTx	Q68PG5	
<i>Centruroides exilicauda</i>	NaTx	Q68PG6	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	P01491	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	Q6V4Z0	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	Q6V4Z1	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	Q95WD3	
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	NaTx	P15223	
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	NaTx	Q6V4Z2	
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	NaTx	P45665	
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	NaTx	Q6V4Z3	
<i>Centruroides exilicauda</i>	NaTx	Q68PG2	
<i>Centruroides limpidus</i>	NaTx	P59865	
<i>Centruroides exilicauda</i>	NaTx	Q68PG4	
<i>Centruroides exilicauda</i>	NaTx	Q68PG7	
<i>Centruroides limpidus</i>	NaTx	Q7Z1K5	
<i>Centruroides limpidus</i>	NaTx	P45666	
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	NaTx	Q9TWL0*	[10-11]
<i>Centruroides limpidus</i>	NaTx	C0HK69*	[12]
<i>Centruroides limpidus</i>	NaTx	Q7Z1K9	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	Q6V4X9	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	Q95WD2	
<i>Centruroides limpidus</i>	NaTx	Q7Z1K8	
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	NaTx	Q9TWL1	

<i>Centruroides infamatus</i>	NaTx	P59897	
<i>Centruroides limpidus</i>	NaTx	P59899	
<i>Centruroides elegans</i>	NaTx	P0CH41*	[13]
<i>Centruroides limpidus</i>	NaTx	P59898*	[14]
<i>Centruroides tecomanus</i>	NaTx	P18926	
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	NaTx	P80076	
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	NaTx	P45662*	[15-16]
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	P56646	
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	NaTx	P01495*	[17-18]
<i>Centruroides suffusus</i>	NaTx	P08900*	[19-22]
<i>Centruroides suffusus</i>	NaTx	P60266*	[23-26]
<i>Centruroides suffusus</i>	NaTx	P0DL83*	[21]
<i>Centruroides suffusus</i>	NaTx	P60267	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	Q95WD1	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	P58778	
<i>Centruroides limpidus</i>	NaTx	Q8WRY4*	[27]
<i>Centruroides exilicauda</i>	NaTx	Q68PG3	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	Q95WC9	
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	NaTx	Q6V4Y2	
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	NaTx	Q94435	
<i>Centruroides gracilis</i>	NaTx	P60163	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	P0CI56	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	P0CI57	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LPA7	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LPA8	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LP86	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LPA9	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	P01494	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	Q6V4Y9	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	P01493	
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	NaTx	P45663*	[28-29]
<i>Centruroides suffusus</i>	NaTx	B7FDP2	
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	NaTx	Q6V4Y8	
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	NaTx	P45664	
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	NaTx	Q6V4Y7	
<i>Centruroides limpidus</i>	NaTx	Q7YT61	
<i>Centruroides limpidus</i>	NaTx	Q7Z1K6	
<i>Centruroides limpidus</i>	NaTx	P45667*	[30-31]
<i>Centruroides limpidus</i>	NaTx	Q7Z1K7	
<i>Centruroides exilicauda</i>	NaTx	Q68PH2	

<i>Centruroides exilicauda</i>	NaTx	Q68PH1	
<i>Centruroides exilicauda</i>	NaTx	Q68PG9	
<i>Centruroides exilicauda</i>	NaTx	Q68PH3	
<i>Centruroides exilicauda</i>	NaTx	Q68PG8	
<i>Centruroides exilicauda</i>	NaTx	Q68PH0	
<i>Centruroides exilicauda</i>	NaTx	Q68PH4	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	Q6V4Y4	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	Q6V4Y3	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	Q6V4Y5	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	Q6V4Y6	
<i>Centruroides limpidus</i>	NaTx	Q7Z1K4	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	P01492	
<i>Megacormus gertschi</i>	NaTx	A0A224XF48	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	P0CI51	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	P0CI53	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	D9U2A0	
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1TZ19	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1TXP5	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	P0CI52	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LPA5	
<i>Centruroides vittatus</i>	NaTx	F8UWP3	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LPC1	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LPC6	
<i>Centruroides elegans</i>	NaTx	P0CH40	
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	H1ZZH9	
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	A0A1E1WW03	
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	C9X4K6	
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	H1ZZH8	
<i>Tityus pachyurus</i>	NaTx	H1ZZI5	
<i>Tityus stigmurus</i>	NaTx	P0C8X5	
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	NaTx	A0A218QX01	
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	NaTx	P01496*	[11] [31-35]
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	NaTx	A0A218QXH0	
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	NaTx	A0A218QWV4	
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	NaTx	P46115	
<i>Tityus fasciolatus</i>	NaTx	P0DSO4	
<i>Tityus bahiensis</i>	NaTx	P0C5K8	
<i>Tityus bahiensis</i>	NaTx	A0A0C9RFQ1	
<i>Tityus bahiensis</i>	NaTx	P56608*	[36]
<i>Parabuthus granulatus</i>	NaTx	B7SNV8	

<i>Parabuthus granulatus</i>	NaTx	POC5F0	
<i>Parabuthus granulatus</i>	NaTx	POC5F1	
<i>Parabuthus transvaalicus</i>	NaTx	P58910	
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	NaTx	E7CLP0	
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	NaTx	E7CLN9	
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	NaTx	E7CLN7	
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	NaTx	E7CLN8	
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	A0A1E1WVY8	
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	H1ZZI3	
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	P46066	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LP99	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LPB0	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	P0CI50	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	D9U2A1	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1SE96	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1SN99	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1TYU4	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1TZJ1	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	P0CI58	
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1SCE1	
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1SEW9	
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1SCD9	
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1TZ49	
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1SEX3	
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1SCE6	
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	NaTx	PODJK8	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1SJ71	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1S5U0	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	D9U297	
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1TYC2	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	P0CI81	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1TYI5	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1TZH3	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	P0CI59	
<i>Lychas mucronatus</i>	NaTx	P0CI60	
<i>Hottentotta judaicus</i>	NaTx	F1CIV2	
<i>Hottentotta judaicus</i>	NaTx	F1CIW7	
Mesobuthus martensii	NaTx	M4GX67*	[37]
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	A0A146CJ61	
Mesobuthus martensii	NaTx	Q9NBW2*	[37-39]

<i>Odontobuthus doriae</i>	NaTx	A0A0U4R446	
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XH17	
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LB09	
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LBX4	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	E4VP15	
<i>Hottentotta judaicus</i>	NaTx	F1CIV8	
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	POC5H3*	[40]
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q9UAC8	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	P86406	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	E4VP18	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	R4H564	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	F6K6F3	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q9UAC9	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	R4H5E1	
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LBV3	
<i>Androctonus mauritanicus</i>	NaTx	PODPT3*	[41]
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	A0A146CIX0	
<i>Centruroides suffusus</i>	NaTx	F1CGT6	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LPA0	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LPA3	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LP93	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LP94	
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LP90	
<i>Centruroides noxius</i>	NaTx	P58296	
<i>Tityus pachyurus</i>	NaTx	H1ZZI8	
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	H1ZZI4	
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	C9X4K4	
<i>Tityus zulianus</i>	NaTx	Q1I165	
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	A0A1E1WVU6	
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	P84693	
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	C9X4J9	
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	C9X4K0	
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	C9X4K1	
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	POC1X7	
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	C9X4K3	
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	POCF39	
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	NaTx	O77463	
<i>Tityus costatus</i>	NaTx	Q5G8A8	
<i>Tityus fasciolatus</i>	NaTx	P83435	
<i>Tityus fasciolatus</i>	NaTx	PODQH6	

<i>Tityus bahiensis</i>	NaTx	A0A0C9S394
<i>Tityus bahiensis</i>	NaTx	P60275
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	H1ZZI1
<i>Tityus bahiensis</i>	NaTx	A0A0C9QKU0
<i>Tityus bahiensis</i>	NaTx	P60276
<i>Tityus fasciolatus</i>	NaTx	A0A098CLT3
<i>Tityus fasciolatus</i>	NaTx	C0HJM9
<i>Tityus bahiensis</i>	NaTx	P56609
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	NaTx	A0A218QWV5
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	NaTx	P68410
<i>Tityus stigmurus</i>	NaTx	P68411
<i>Tityus clathratus</i>	NaTx	J9PIJ6
<i>Tityus stigmurus</i>	NaTx	P56612
<i>Tityus bahiensis</i>	NaTx	A0A0C9QKV7
<i>Tityus fasciolatus</i>	NaTx	P0DQH5
<i>Tityus bahiensis</i>	NaTx	P56611
<i>Tityus bahiensis</i>	NaTx	A0A0C9RFN5
<i>Tityus serrulatus</i>	NaTx	P15226*
<i>Tityus costatus</i>	NaTx	Q5G8B8
<i>Tityus trivittatus</i>	NaTx	P0DMM8
<i>Tityus fasciolatus</i>	NaTx	P0DSO5
<i>Tityus clathratus</i>	NaTx	J9PJ66
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	A0A1E1WVT2
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	A0A1E1WWK4
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	A0A1E1WVW4
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	H1ZZH7
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	Q1I176
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	Q1I180
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	A0A1E1WWE3
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	P60212
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	A0A1E1WVW0
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	P60215
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	Q1I173
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	C9X4J8
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	Q1I177
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	Q1I164
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	Q1I178
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	Q1I163
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	Q1I169
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	Q1I179

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<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	Q1I172
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	Q1I167
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	P0CF37
<i>Tityus discrepans</i>	NaTx	Q1I174
<i>Tityus zulianus</i>	NaTx	Q2NME3
<i>Tityus pachyurus</i>	NaTx	P84631
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	A0A1E1WVS8
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	P60214
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	H1ZZI0
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	A0A1E1WVN9
<i>Tityus obscurus</i>	NaTx	P60213
<i>Centruroides sculpturatus</i>	NaTx	P58779
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	NaTx	P86992
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	NaTx	E7CLP3
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	NaTx	E7CLP4
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	NaTx	E7CLP5
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	NaTx	E7CLP2
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	NaTx	E7CLN0
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	NaTx	E7CLN5
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	NaTx	E7CLN6
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	NaTx	E7CLN3
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	NaTx	E7CLN4
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	NaTx	E7CLN2
<i>Heteroctenus junceus</i>	NaTx	E7CLN1
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LP97
<i>Centruroides hentzi</i>	NaTx	A0A2I9LPA6
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1S864
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1SEV0
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1TZA2
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1SCC7
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	NaTx	P0DJK9
<i>Buthus tunetanus</i>	NaTx	P59863
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XH11
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XH07
<i>Androctonus australis</i>	NaTx	P81504
<i>Androctonus crassicauda</i>	NaTx	M1INJ1
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	P68725
<i>Isometrus maculatus</i>	NaTx	A0A0U1S623
<i>Odontobuthus doriae</i>	NaTx	A0A0U4PXU5
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XH12

<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XH10
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XH16
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XH18
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XH13
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XH20
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XH14
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XH19
<i>Hottentotta tamulus</i>	NaTx	P82814
<i>Hottentotta tamulus</i>	NaTx	P82812
<i>Hottentotta tamulus</i>	NaTx	P82813
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XH08
<i>Orthochirus scrobiculosus</i>	NaTx	O76963
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XH09
<i>Buthus tunetanus</i>	NaTx	P59864
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	P81240
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	P0C514
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	P0C518
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	P0C519
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	P0C516
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	P0C513
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	P0C515
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	P0C517
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	P0C5J0
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LBW5
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LBV6
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LCI1
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LBV0
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LBW4
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LBW0
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LCI0
<i>Odontobuthus doriae</i>	NaTx	A0A0U4QNN2
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	A0A146CIR0
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LCH7
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LBU8
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LBV4
<i>Androctonus bicolor</i>	NaTx	A0A0K0LBT5
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	P68726
<i>Leiurus hebraeus</i>	NaTx	Q26292
<i>Hottentotta judaicus</i>	NaTx	F1CJ38
<i>Hottentotta saulcyi</i>	NaTx	Q2NNB8

<i>Hottentotta judaicus</i>	NaTx	F1CIX9	
<i>Hottentotta judaicus</i>	NaTx	P24336	
<i>Buthus tunetanus</i>	NaTx	P55904	
<i>Buthacus arenicola</i>	NaTx	P80962	
<i>Buthus tunetanus</i>	NaTx	P55903	
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XH21	
<i>Hottentotta tamulus</i>	NaTx	P82811	
<i>Leiurus quinquestriatus</i>	NaTx	P19855	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	A0A146CIQ1	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	A0A146CIT8	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	A0A146CIU6	
<i>Mesobuthus eupeus</i>	NaTx	A0A146CIV1	
<i>Buthus israelis</i>	NaTx	B8XH15	
<i>Mesobuthus gibbosus</i>	NaTx	A0A059UED5	
<i>Mesobuthus gibbosus</i>	NaTx	A0A059UI27	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q86M31	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q95WX6	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q8I0K7	[47]
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q17230	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q7Z1E1	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q9BKJ0	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	P15228	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q8T3T0	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q9XY87*	[48]
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q9BKJ1	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q17231	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	A9Q1X9	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	P68727	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	A9Q1Y1	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	A9Q1Y0	
<i>Mesobuthus martensii</i>	NaTx	Q9Y1U3	

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